

Oxidation of Diethyl Malate by Chromic Acid and Relative Rates of Oxidation of Malic Acid and the Ester

D. S. Jha* and G. V. Bakore

The kinetics of the initial stages of oxidation of diethyl malate by chromic acid have been studied. The rate is proportional to the concentrations of HCrO_4^- , ester and hydrogen ions. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. The main product of oxidation is oxalacetic acid ester. The rate of oxidation of malic acid and its ester have been compared. The slow rate of oxidation for ester has been explained on the basis of inductive effect and steric effect.

Recently, chromic acid oxidation of the esters of some hydroxy acids have been studied by some workers^{1,2}. The data reported are very limited and it seems the kinetics of these reactions has not been properly understood. We now report the chromic acid oxidation of diethyl malate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material : Chromic acid solution was prepared from "AnalaR" potassium dichromate. Glacial acetic acid, MnSO_4 and other reagents used were chemically pure. Diethyl malate was prepared by Fischer's method³ and purified by redistillation.

Kinetic Measurements : The experiments were carried out at constant temperature ($\pm 0.2^\circ$). The solvent used was 50% acetic acid. Ionic strength was kept constant by use of potassium sulphate. Sulphuric acid was used as the source of hydrogen ions. Since the concentration of dichromate was much smaller than those of the ester and hydrogen ions, the hydrogen ion concentration did not change appreciably during the course of the experiment⁴. To calculate hydrogen ion concentration, *pH* was measured. Reactions were followed by withdrawing aliquots at known interval of time and the gross concentration of Cr(VI) was estimated by iodometric method⁵.

RESULTS

Rate Laws : When concentration of ester and hydrogen ions were high, it was found that the rate at which Cr(VI) disappears follows first order law. HCrO_4^- appears to be the active oxidising species⁶.

The rate is proportional to the first power of hydrogen ion concentration and also to the first power of the concentration of ester (cf. Table 1). Increase in the proportion of acetic

* With whom all correspondence should be made.

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acid in the solvent mixture (acetic acid and water) increases the rate of oxidation (cf. Table 1). In presence of acetic acid the rate of oxidation is affected by one or more of the following factors : (i) increase in acetic acid decreases dielectric constant⁷ of the solvent and consequently increases the protonation of HCrO_4^- , which leads to increased rate of oxidation. (ii) the possibility of the formation of acetyl chromic acid $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCrO}_2\text{OH}$ or its conjugated acid $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCrO}_2\text{OH}_2^+$, in acetic acid medium. These are strong acids and more powerful oxidising agents compared to chromic acid^{8,9}. It is however, difficult to precisely state the contribution of each factor with increase in the proportion of acetic acid in solvent mixture.

TABLE 1

Chromic Acid Oxidation of Diethyl Malate

{[Cr(VI)] : $4.00 \times 10^{-3}M$; Temperature 35° }

(H ⁺)/M	$10^2(\text{Ester})/M$	%AcOH(v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^5/\text{s}^{-1}$	$k_2 \times 10^3$ 1 mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.15	—	50	—	0.68
0.30	—	50	—	1.40
0.42	—	50	—	1.81
0.60	—	50	—	2.72
1.6*	0.52	50	3.2	—
1.6	1.05	50	6.2	—
1.6	1.58	50	9.3	—
1.6	2.10	50	12.8	—
1.6	—	20	—	2.46
1.6	—	40	—	4.63
1.6	—	80	—	8.41

* Calculated value.

Addition of manganous ions decreases the rate of oxidation. The rate reaches a limiting value when concentration of manganous ions $2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, and under these conditions the rate of oxidation in presence of manganous ions is about half the rate in absence of manganous ions. This result is expected if the manganous ions catalyse the disproportionation of the intermediate valency state of chromium, and indicate that chromium(IV) is probably involved as an intermediate^{5,10,11,12} (cf. Table 2).

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TABLE 2

Effect of Manganous Ions [Mn(II)] on Rate
 {[Cr(VI)] : $4.00 \times 10^{-3}M$; (H⁺) : $1.6M$; Temp. 35°}

[Mn(II)]/M	$10^3 k_2/s^{-1} \text{ l mol}^{-1}$
—	6.31
2.0	6.12
6.0	4.75
10.0	4.51
20.0	3.31

Effect of Temperature : The reaction was studied at temperatures 25, 32, 35 and 40°. The rate constants at these temperatures have been recorded in Table 3, column 2. Bakore and Narain⁴ have shown that when [Cr(VI)] $\simeq 4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, the whole of the chromium exists as HCrO_4^- . In our experimental conditions also [Cr(VI)] $\simeq (\text{HCrO}_4^-)$, the specific rates were therefore, obtained from the observed pseudo first order rate constants from the relation :

$$k = k_1/(\text{Ester})(\text{H}^+)$$

These are given in Table 3, column 3. The heat of activation, PZ factor and the entropy of activation, calculated from data in Table 3, have the value 11.8 kcal mol⁻¹, $1.01 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and -32 e.u. respectively.

TABLE 3

Effect of Temperature
 [(Ester) : $1.05 \times 10^{-2}M$; {Cr(VI)} : $4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; (H⁺)

Temperature °K	$10^5 k_1/s^{-1}$	$10^3 k/1^2 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
298	3.13	1.87
305	5.07	3.02
308	6.23	3.71
313	8.30	4.94

DISCUSSION

The rate laws for the oxidation of diethyl malate are similar to the rate laws for similar oxidations of malic acid⁴ and secondary alcohols^{10,12,13}, which also contain -CHOH group. The value for the energy of activation and entropy of activation for isopropyl alcohol¹² and malic acid⁴ are 12 kcal/mol, 8.3 kcal/mol, and -34 e.u. and -37 e.u. respectively. These values are of the same order as have been observed for the oxidation of diethyl malate. Oxidation of malic acid and isopropyl alcohol involves the rupture of C-H bond on carbon

atom. It is, therefore, reasonable to suppose that oxidation of diethyl malate also involves the rupture of this bond.

To explain the order of the rates for oxidation of hydroxy acids, it has been proposed by Bakore and Narain⁴ that in the rupture of C-H bond hydrogen is lost as proton. This indicates support to the mechanism suggested by Kwart and Francis¹⁴ for the oxidation of cyclic secondary alcohols (proton loss theory). As these facts are in agreement with our observations for the relative rates of oxidation for malic acid and diethylmalate, the scheme of proton loss seems satisfactory for the oxidation of diethyl malate by chromic acid. The product analysis (see below) shows that oxalacetic ester is the main product of oxidation. The following mechanism is therefore, proposed.

As the mechanism for the oxidation of malic acid and diethyl malate is similar, it will be instructive to compare the rates for oxidation of the two. Such a comparison is brought about in Table 4.

TABLE 4

Compound	$10^2 k_2$ 1/mol s			
	25°	30°	35°	40°
Malic Acid	4.5	5.9	7.4	8.9
Diethyl malate	0.15	0.27	0.37	0.49

The slow rate of oxidation for ester could be due to the possibility of its hydrolysis, however, the high yield of oxalacetic ester rules out such a possibility. These oxidations are shown to involve proton loss and such a process will be helped by the stronger -I effect of -COOH group compared to -COOEt group and so the oxidation of the acid will be faster. There is yet another possibility of steric effect of ethyl group hindering the formation of chromate ester and thus reducing the rate of oxidation for ester. In brief, all these factors put together account for the slow rate of oxidation for ester compared to that of acid.

Product Analysis : The main product of oxidation was found to be the oxalacetic acid ester. It was identified and estimated as its D.N.P., and the yield was about 89%.

Chemical Laboratories,
University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur.

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